

November-January. The thallus initially was oval or spherical and slightly gelatinous. After full growth it was hollow and brownish.

To implement the BGA technology in

Influence of nitrogen topdressing on the performance of blue-green algae

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The usefulness of blue-green algae (BGA) under nitrogen levels as high as 100 kg/ha was established earlier. To assess the influence of topdressing of nitrogen fertilizer on BGA performance, a trial was conducted in kharif 1979 with the variety ADT31. Nitrogen fertilizer was tried at rates as high as 100 kg/ha in slabs of 25 kg. A composite culture of BGA was applied uniformly to treatments a week after planting. Various nitrogen levels were applied with BGA both with and without topdressing of 25 kg N/ha 35 days after transplanting. The crop was harvested early in October. Topdressing of nitrogen fertilizer at 25 to 100 kg N/ha had no inhibitory effect on BGA performance. Yield data follow:

Treatments (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N ₀ +BGA 10	3.8
N ₀ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	4.2
N ₂₅ +BGA 10	4.2
N ₂₅ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	4.6
N ₅₀ +BGA 10	4.5
N ₅₀ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	5.0
N ₇₅ +BGA 10	4.9
N ₇₅ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	5.3
N ₁₀₀ +BGA	5.4
N ₁₀₀ + BGA N 25 topdressing	5.8
C.D. (C : 0.05%)	0.3

Effects of drying on the germinability of newly harvested rice seeds

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Poor seed germination is a problem because farmers do not know how to

Tamil Nadu, the 12 BGA types will be multiplied in 1981 and distributed to State seed farms for further multiplication before distribution to farmers. ■

handle newly harvested rice seeds. The problem increases with double-cropping if the first crop is a new variety. Most improved rice varieties are weakly or moderately dormant, and so farmers are often short of seedlings and must leave portions of their fields unplanted.

An experiment using seeds of the early-maturing IR50 was conducted at the NONAS Experiment Farm in October 1980 with two objectives: to determine the effect of the number of drying days on germinability of newly harvested rice, and to find the relation between "rest days" after drying and germination percentage.

The rag doll was used: 100 selected IR50 seeds/treatment were sun-dried (on *sawali* at 6 kg seeds/m²) from 0700 to 1500 hours for 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days then soaked in water and incubated for 48, 72, and 96 hours, respectively. The seeds were sown in a seedbed, then germination percentages were recorded every 48, 72, and 96 hours, respectively.

The germinability of newly harvested rice seeds increased with the number of days of sun-drying and with the number of days the seeds were allowed to "rest"

after drying.

Germination was maximum when the seeds were dried continuously for 4 days, "rested" for 6 days, then soaked in clean water and incubated for 48 hours.

When seeds were dried from 0 to 2 days, germination was slow (beginning 24 hours to 96 hours after incubation) and nonuniform. Rice seeds dried from 3 to 5 days germinated uniformly; germination ended within 48 hours of incubation.

The farmer can expect 10% germination if immediately after harvest he cleans rice seeds and soaks them in clean water for 24 hours, then incubates them for the next 48 hours. Drying for 1 day would give a germination of 17%; drying for 4 or 5 days, 93% (see figure).

We found that 70% of the viable seeds will sprout if induced to germinate without a rest period. One day of rest results in about 75% germination of viable seeds; 2 days will give 80%; 4 days, 90%; 5 days, 95%; and 6 days, 100%.

For germinability in relation to the interval of days of drying, the study showed a 42% increase with 0-1 day drying, 71% with 1-2 days drying, 28% with 2-3 days, 10% with 3-4 days, and 0.1% with 4-5 days.

Thus, there is no need to dry newly harvested rice seeds more than 4 days if the seeds are to be used immediately for the next crop. ■

Germination (%)

Average percentage germination of newly harvested IR50 rice seeds with respect to length of drying. Negros Oriental, Philippines.